

CURRICULUM VITAE

1971

ANDREW GEORGE WILLIAMSON.

HOME ADDRESS: Ollaberry,
Grimms Hill,
Great Missenden,
Bucks,
ENGLAND.

BORN: 18/12/1945

AGE: 25 years.

EDUCATION: Rugby School, Rugby, Warwickshire, England. 1959-1963.
Certificate in Spanish Language and civilization,
Madrid University. 1964.
Pembroke College, Oxford University. 1964-1967.
Honours Degree in Modern History 1967.
Research Student at Pembroke College and
The Queen's College, Oxford From 1967.
Submission of Doctoral Dissertation for the Department
of Oriental Studies, Oxford University 1972

LANGUAGES: Spanish-very good. German-poor.
Portuguese-good. Persian-fair.
Latin-good. Arabic-very poor.
French-good.

PUBLICATIONS: "Islamic Trade Routes in Southern Iran", Iran VIII, 1970,
pp. 202-203.
"Excavations at Sirjan", Iran IX, 1971, p. 177.
"Excavations at Tepe Dasht-i-Deh", Iran IX, 1971,
pp. 182-183.
"Gulf Commerce in the Sassanian Period and the first
two centuries of Islam", Bostan Shenav va Honar-i-Iran,
30 pp., in press.

- "Excavations at Tepe Dasht-i-Deh", Iran X, 1972, in press.
- "Excavations at Sirjan", full excavation report in preparation for Iran, XI, 1973.
- "Excavations at Tepe Dasht-i-Deh", full excavation report in preparation for The Papers of the Peabody Museum, Harvard University.
- "Archaeological and Documentary Material for the History and Mechanisms of Commerce in Southern Iran from the Seventh Century A.D. to the End of the Portuguese Period".
 Doctoral thesis for submission to Oxford University, 1972.

FELLOWSHIPS AND GRANTS: Department of Education and Science Major State Studentship. 1967-1969. Renewed 1969-1970.

Fellow of the British Institute of Persian Studies. 1968-1969. Renewed 1969-1970.

Honourary Fellow of the British Institute of Persian Studies. 1970-1971.

Randall-MacIver Student of the Queen's College, Oxford. 1971-1973.

Grantee of the Wainwright Fund for Near Eastern Archaeology of the University of Oxford. 1970-1971. For archaeological survey in Southern Iran.

Grantee of the Stein-Arnold Fund of the British Academy. 1969. For excavations at Sirjan.

Grantee of the Meyerstein Research Fund of the University of Oxford. 1969. For excavations at Sirjan.

Grantee of the Siraf Fund of the British Institute of Persian Studies. 1969. For excavations at Sirjan,